

ACUTE - Accessibility and Connectivity Knowledge Hub for Urban Transformation in Europe

WP3 – Practitioner Interaction

D3.4.5 Report on French national pilot workshop

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Project Partners

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1. French National Pilot workshop

1.1. Goals of the event

The National Pilot workshop as organized during the Mobility days of Strasbourg.

Our goal, by organizing the French national pilot workshop during the Mobility day – Strasbourg :

- To be in touch with a network of French practitioners working in the field of Mobility and Urbanism
- To assess their familiarity with the concept of a 15-minute City
- To create a space for exchange between French practitioners and stimulate shared experiences

ENGLISH VERSION

Registrations closed

Mobility in the regions: the challenge of demand

Faced with the ecological emergency and the need to decarbonise mobility, local and regional authorities are mobilised and developing ambitious public policies in a context marked by an accumulation of crises (health, energy, economic, etc.) that are having a major impact on their financial capacities. Supply policies to develop active modes of transport or the use of public transport run the risk of generating demand that is increasingly difficult and costly to satisfy, or of coming up against unsustainable mobility desires. **So how do you reconcile supply and demand for mobility?**

This issue will be at the heart of the **6th European Mobility Days in Strasbourg**, organised on 16 and 17 May 2024 by **Cerema** and **CNFPT**, in partnership with the **Eurometropole of Strasbourg**, **GART**, **UTP**, **MOT**, **UGE**, **ADEUS** (Strasbourg Urban Planning Agency), and the **European POLIS network**. The aim of these days is to discuss and exchange ideas based on European and international examples, in order to compare and understand the issues and levers for action, and thus act effectively to promote a sustainable mobility policy.

These days will be divided into 4 main sessions:

1. **Residents and regions**: can expectations be reconciled?
2. **Public spaces**: new uses, new sharing
3. Round table: **'Is the city of proximity a long way off?'**
4. **Public transport**, between multimodality and financial constraints

On the first day, the **French National pilot workshop of the European ACUTE programme** will also be held.

PARTENAIRES

1.2. Focus on the participants

27 practitioners with different professional background attended to the workshop:

- Territorial Authorities: 59%
- NGOs : 22%
- Private Sector : 19%

The majority of attendees had a transport and mobility background. Some of them worked in the field of city adaptation to climate change, urbanism, energy, telecom and digital.

1.3. The workshop program

The Workshop was built with 3 configuration questions:

- How does the 15-minute City concept echo with your professional practice ?
- Which words to define the concept of a 15-minute City ?
- How research and practice can collaborate to bring proximity in our cities ?

There were a restitution part through 3 defining elements that should appear in the pitch :

- The concept's echo on the practical collaboration between research and practice
- Participants would define the concepts through subjective essential components

2. Outcomes of the workshop

- The majority of the participants were familiar with the 15-minute City concept.
- Inclusivity (gender, reduced mobility...) came out as the key component of the concept and should be the focus of urban development.
- The majority of the participants were not convinced with the nomenclature "15-minute City" and were more keen to use the "City of Proximity".
- Some participants expressed the fear of "ghettoization" and "in-betweenness" in the implementation of the concept.
- Visibility and visualization of accessible services must be improved in the 15-minute City.
- Some participants declared that active modes and public transport should be privileged modes of the 15-minute City.
- Other participants expressed that cars can't be excluded In the 15-min City model; carsharing should be promoted in order to include rural and peri-urban areas in the concept's storytelling.
- Collaboration between Research and Practice: "Research-action" model illustrated by some organization as POPSU should be the norm in the implementation of urban concepts as 15-min City, as is the case in some major French cities